

Requirement cards

Privacy against other users

How to protect against malicious users of who can reconstruct the data of other users whose data were used to train/update the recommendation system?

Privacy Vs fairness

Constraining ML algorithms to be fair obliges the algorithms to learn from **minorities** in the data exposing them to higher risks of leakage. How can that be addressed?

Fairness

Sensitive features such as race, gender, and age may be encoded in correlations between other insensitive features. How to ensure that the elimination of some sensitive features is successful ?

Fairness Through Awareness

Should Hoggle curate the dataset to achieve demographic parity (or a fairness metric of your choosing) in the outcomes of the hiring system at the cost of making the sample unrepresentative?

Feature Audit

Should the “collaborative skills” feature be reexamined since it may remove the disparate impact?

Fairness Through Unawareness

Should Hoggle continue to rely on their approach of not including the protected attribute as a feature?

Legal Manipulation?

How is the current design of consent using dark patterns justified or not? Would it be legal?

Training

Privacy concerns require adequate training to understand what is important to communicate. What kind of training is offered?

Legalese or Overkill?

How is relevant information conveyed to stakeholders considering the tradeoff between specificity and legal generality?

Communication is Blind

How are the stakeholders informed about the data processing (e.g., AI, dark patterns) practices given how difficult it is to communicate?

Privacy

The building of models in third party servers includes leaving copies of data that are personal in those servers. How can such a risk be addressed?

Security Threats

The quality of the security measures should be assessed based on how well they address the threat models. What is the best strategy to design a performant threat model ?

Instructions

Role play game

Welcome!

In the CR2 role play game where multiple teams are given a fictional scenario. The goal is to discuss elements of trust and transparency in data processing in complex social, legal, and technical situations with two teams competing against each other.

Instructions

The Jury chooses a scenario to set the stage.

The Green team chooses a requirement card and builds a strategy to fulfill it. The Blue team takes notes and argues against the Green team. At the end of each round the Jury chooses a winner. *See instructions for different win conditions.*

Mini Instruction Cards

Green team

You go first to draw a requirements card. You have 5min to read the related information and answer the requirements card in another 5min .

Blue team

Take notes on the Green team's strategy. You go second. 5min to question the Green team and build an adversarial strategy in 5min.

Jury Deliberation

5min for the jury to deliberate and choose a winner, with clear reasoning of why.

Jury and Player Cards

Jury Member

Congrats! You are on the Jury. You will be judging the Green and Blue team strategies.

Player

Congrats! You are a player. You will be coming up with strategies to win over the Jury.

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Player Only Cards

Player

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**scenario cards: see Definitions
sheet for more detail**

Dark or Light?

Toomtoom is a medium-sized marketing company that is trying to gain a larger foothold in the market. They follow current trends for data privacy, security (ISO standards), AI for showing personalized ads, and informed consent that use dark patterns to get more customers. While it is a gray area for being legally compliant given that everyone follows the same dark patterns, they are considering building brand loyalty by positioning themselves as an extremely trustworthy and transparent company. Toomtoom now seeks to understand if this public trust can be built with dark patterns or if it is worth putting in extra effort to use other methods.

Hired or Fired?

Hoggle Inc., a leading tech company, has implemented a machine learning algorithm for hiring. The algorithm, designed to identify the most suitable candidates, leads to the hiring of significantly more women than men. The algorithm heavily weighs "collaborative skills," which, due to various social and educational factors, is more common the profiles of female candidates. This has led to a disproportionate hiring of women over men, even though the sensitive attribute was not used to train the hiring system. Hoggle Inc. now seeks to understand whether their perceived public trust will be affected by this practice and guidance on their next steps.

Green v Blue cards

Team selection

You are the Blue team !

Team selection

You are the Green team
!

Team selection

You are the Blue team !

Team selection

You are the Green team
!

Team selection

You are the Blue team !

Team selection

You are the Green team
!